

Developing An Animated 3D Model of Ab Barak Land Slide on Microsoft Hololens

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction	02
---------------------	-----------

Development Tools	05
--------------------------	-----------

- Microsoft Hololens
 - Computer Running on Windows 10
 - Wifi Connection
 - Hololens Windows App
 - Microsoft Hololens Emulator
 - Esri CityEngine
 - Microsoft Visual Studio
 - Unity 3D
-

Development Process	09
----------------------------	-----------

- Applying Texture on the Terrain
 - Some Approaches to Animate the Landslide
 - Shaping and Contouring the Plane or Terrain
 - Animating the Landslide
 - Adding the Barrier Lake
 - Displaying the Video, Image and Text
 - Applying Rain Animation
 - Applying Gesture Command
 - Applying Voice Command
-

Evaluation	18
<hr/>	
Conclusion	18
<hr/>	
Future Works	18
<hr/>	
Acknowledgement	19
<hr/>	
Reference	19

1. INTRODUCTION

An autonomous UN body established in 1963, the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (www.unitar.org) is a training arm of the United Nations System, and has the mandate to enhance the effectiveness of the UN through diplomatic training, and to increase the impact of national actions through public awareness-raising, education and training of public policy officials.

UNITAR provides training and capacity development activities to assist mainly developing countries with special attention to Least Developed Countries (LDCs), Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and other groups and communities who are most vulnerable, including those in conflict situations. The Institute covers topics in the broad areas of supporting capacity for the 2030 Agenda, strengthening multilateralism, advancing environmental sustainability and green development, improving resilience and humanitarian assistance, promoting sustainable peace, and promoting economic development and social inclusion. It also conducts research on innovative learning approaches, methods, and tools, as well as applied research to address critical issues, such as disaster risk reduction and humanitarian emergencies.

UNOSAT (UNITAR's Operational Satellite Applications Programme) is a technology-intensive programme delivering imagery analysis and satellite solutions to relief and develop organisations within and outside the UN system to help make a difference in critical areas such as humanitarian relief, human security, strategic territorial and development planning. UNOSAT develops applied research solutions keeping in sight the needs of the beneficiaries at the end of the process.

Figure 1 An overview of the Ab Barak landslide which occurred on 2 May 2014 in Badakshan, Afghanistan. There is an old landslide (with unknown age) next to the recent one, indicating that this region is prone to landslide hazards. The white dashed lines show the

CERN as one of the biggest research institution in the world has a partnership with UNOSAT to do a research in the field of disaster relief. There are several research project being conducted to address the need of both institutions. In this document, the project that will be explained is about developing a 3D model of Ab Barak landslide on Microsoft Hololens, an Augmented Reality (AR) technology introduced by Microsoft. The Ab Barak landslide is chosen to be animated on Microsoft Hololens for two purposes, which are: to learn about developing application on Microsoft Hololens and to present the actual disaster data that relevant to UNOSAT.

The Ab Barak landslide which occurred on 2 May 2014 in Badakshan, Afghanistan was induced by heavy rainfall in the period of 25 to 29 April. This event has drawn a lot of international attention due to its large magnitude and devastating damage. The number of fatalities remains uncertain, ranging from 300 to more than 2700. UNOSAT's mapping of the landslide impacts shows that a total of 87 structures were certainly buried by the landslide based on comparison of the WorldView-2 satellite images from 7 June 2013, the date of the pre-event image used for comparison, and the image from 5 May 2014. It is likely that the damage might be underestimated because of the expansion of the village between 7 June 2013 and the occurrence of the landslide (<http://www.unitar.org/unosat/node/44/1991>).

Apart from the direct damage, the landslide also blocked the Barik Aab valley, forming a landslide dam and a barrier lake. The local authority is facing the challenge of dealing with the dam in order to reduce the possible uncontrolled dam-breach flood hazard. Possible solutions such as constructing a temporal channel to release the water and a permanent spillway in the dry season were discussed.

2. Development Tools

These are the hardware and software needed to develop the Ab Barak 3D model on Microsoft HoloLens. Some software may have dependency to others. All the information about the tools and tutorial can be found on the following links. There is no ultimate tutorial to set the things up since there are various available development approach.

- **Developer readiness status**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/developer_readiness_status)
- **How to Get Started Creating for Windows Mixed Reality**
(<https://hololens.reality.news/how-to/hololens-dev-101-get-started-creating-for-windows-mixed-reality-0174598/>)
- **Set up HoloLens**
(<https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/hololens/hololens-setup>)
- **How to Install & Set Up the Software to Start Developing for Windows Holographic**
(<https://hololens.reality.news/how-to/hololens-dev-101-install-set-up-software-start-developing-for-windows-holographic-0174683/>)
- **Using the Windows Device Portal**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/using_the_windows_device_portal)
- **Using Visual Studio**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/using_visual_studio)
- **Get apps for HoloLens**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/get_apps_for_hololens#from_the_windows_store)
- **How to Install & Set Up the HoloLens Emulator**
(<https://hololens.reality.news/how-to/hololens-dev-101-install-set-up-hololens-emulator-0174845/>)
- **Install the tools**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/install_the_tools)
- **How to Build a Basic HoloLens App in Minutes**
(<https://hololens.reality.news/how-to/hololens-dev-101-build-basic-hololens-app-minutes-0175021/>)
- **Holograms 100**
(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/holograms_100#chapter_1_-_create_a_new_project)
- **Holograms 101**

(https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/holograms_101)

- **HoloLens Mixed Reality Streaming Done Right**
(<https://vbandi.net/2016/08/18/hololens-mixed-reality-streaming-done-right/>)
- **Microsoft/MixedRealityToolkit-Unity**
(<https://github.com/Microsoft/MixedRealityToolkit-Unity>)
- **How To: Export textured models from CityEngine into Unity**
(<http://support.esri.com/en/technical-article/000012449>)
- **Examples - CityEngine and Unity**
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xaPDmuotjWU>)
- **Unity Tutorial 4 - How to apply materials, shaders and textures to objects in Unity**
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MGIBLPiz4oM>)
- **Unity Tutorial 5 - Adding terrain, trees and water to your game**
(https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OD88_KGYXbg)

Summing up all the information available on the links above, here are the configured tools that finally works during the development of this project. The step by step installation details for each point can be found on the links above.

a. Microsoft HoloLens

Figure 2 HoloLens is worn by the user to see the unseen (virtual / holographic model)

Microsoft HoloLens or simply called HoloLens is a device developed by Microsoft that capable of merging a virtual world with the real one. HoloLens is built to deliver a mixed reality experience to another level by integrating multiple sensors and build-in SDK capabilities on such a compact device. It is a mobile device gadget since it has its own computing power. There are some well developed features on this headset, such as: voice recognition, gesture recognition, and spatial mapping.

b. Computer Running on Windows 10

Windows 10 is the most fundamental need for the developer. A fresh installed windows 10 is better since the next software, Visual Studio and Unity 3D, need a specific Windows SDK. It is possible to install any

other software besides the software for developing the HoloLens app, but the Windows SDK might not be suitable and could lead to an application crash. However, Microsoft has been trying to address some issues and the dependency should be getting better over time.

c. Wifi Connection

A wifi is needed to connect the HoloLens to the desktop. The first time you use your HoloLens, you'll be guided through connecting to a Wi-Fi network. You need to connect HoloLens to a Wi-Fi network with Internet connectivity so that the user account can be authenticated.

- It can be an open Wi-Fi or password-protected Wi-Fi network.
- The Wi-Fi network cannot require you to navigate to a webpage to connect.
- The Wi-Fi network cannot require certificates to connect.
- The Wi-Fi network does not need to provide access to enterprise resources or intranet sites.

If necessary, the MAC address can be added manually to the network. Getting the MAC address is as simple as connecting the HoloLens to any mobile-tethered open wifi and then write down the address by looking at the list of connected devices on that network. A stable wifi is also important for supporting auto sync any media file uploaded to its dedicated cloud server. Whenever a picture is taken or a video is recorded using HoloLens, the file is uploaded to the cloud and can be downloaded by visiting its IP address. In addition, a pairing between the HoloLens and the developer's desktop is easier to be done over the wifi connection as well. Therefore, getting this device connected to the internet is a priority.

d. HoloLens Windows App

Unlike any other gadget device that can be sync by wire, HoloLens requires a special built-in app to be installed in the desktop as well as in the HoloLens to support the development process. In the desktop, the app can be downloaded in the Windows Store. Microsoft only provides the app for US developers because the HoloLens is currently only sold in the US. However, any desktop could be set as if it is located in the US region to download the app. The location setting can be found on the Settings menu.

e. Microsoft HoloLens Emulator

The emulator is available to test out the app without actually deploying to HoloLens. However, this project is not suitable since it needs some inputs such as gesture and voice command. The function of HoloLens Emulator is much like making sure the app was deployable. It is better to use the real HoloLens to speed up the testing and debugging process.

f. Esri CityEngine

CityEngine models can be exported to Wavefront OBJ files along with any associated textures and opened in the 3D game engine, Unity. However, issues with drawing models in Unity may arise if export settings are not set correctly. The details of the exporting process could be read from the links listed in the description. In this project, the terrain of Ab Barak is cropped from the actual height map of earth taken by the satellite. Then, the selected area is exported so that it can be used in Unity 3D for further development.

g. Microsoft Visual Studio

Microsoft Visual Studio (VS) is used to deploy the app to Microsoft HoloLens or to the emulator. It seems a simple role, but Microsoft makes it harder to set up since the App is originally developed and built on Unity

3D. The build setting on Unity 3D has to match with the Windows SDK where the Visual Studio is running on. In the installation process, the Windows SDK could be selected manually. That action is mandatory because not every SDK is supported by Hololens. If the SDK version is too high or too low, the VS cannot connect to the Hololens and the deployment process will fail. However, there is no specific official explanation about that. This project is using SDK version 10.0.10240.0. If the SDK on that version is not working, there are two options to work around. First, just uninstall and reinstall the VS with choosing another SDK version. Second, uninstall the current SDK and install manually another SDK that can be downloaded from Microsoft official sites. The SDK should be supported by your current OS version as well. Therefore, setting up VS to deploy the app to Hololens is such a complex process.

Figure 3 Visual Studio version used in this development

h. Unity 3D

Figure 4 Unity 3D version used in this development

Microsoft and Unity have been working closely to provide Unity developers the tools to create Mixed Reality (MR) applications for HoloLens. Microsoft developer also provide a plugin for Unity called HoloToolkit. The HoloToolkit is a collection of scripts and components intended to accelerate the development of holographic applications targeting Windows Holographic. Once the HoloToolkit source is added to Assets folder on Unity 3D project, an additional menu called Holotoolkit will appear automatically at menu bar. Actually the menu is only giving shortcuts to set some parameters related to Windows Holographic project. Without HoloToolkit, all those parameters could be set manually using the normal menus. Beside of that, Unity 3D has an important effect on the building process. The parameters on Build Settings should comply with the the SDK of installed Visual Studio as shown in the picture below.

Figure 5 Pay attention on the target SDK being used by Visual Studio

3. Development Process

In this section, the required tools are already installed. The development process is covering the detail of feature implementation and the process of animating Ab Barak Landslide. The development is started by animating the landslide using various techniques and choose the best one. Afterwards, put some information around the scene including the report from UNITAR and the video news. For the ease of understanding, please watch the final demo of this project entitled “**Ab-Barak Landslide in 3D Model**” at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AT0qYbjEzzw&t=1s>

a. Applying Texture on the Terrain

Figure 6 Fresh terrain in Unity 3D (exported from CityEngine)

First we need the .fbx terrain exported from CityEngine. That file could be imported to our Unity project as a new assets. Just drag and drop the object to the scene and set the proper position. The imported object from CityEngine is a bare white looking terrain that needs a new skin/material attached to its surface. The surface is taken from Google Maps as shown in the Figure 4. The image will be used as texture and can be put by dragging it to the terrain surface. Example of the detail work could be watched at the link above entitled "Unity Tutorial 4 - How to apply materials, shaders and textures to objects in Unity".

Figure 7 Google maps satellite image (after the landslide)

b. Some Approaches to Animate the Landslide

After setting up the terrain and its texture material, the landslide is ready to be animated. The most important fact in this step so far is the 3D terrain model is the condition of after landslide. Therefore it is match with the texture that is taken by Google maps in 2017. The animation is needed to show the before and after the disaster, especially to depict how the mud is flooding the village. Any additional object or particle is needed to fill up the sand/hill that was existed before the disaster occurs. That object should imitate the mud going down from the top of the hill flooding the inhabited valley.

Figure 8 The terrain after landslide happen

Besides, there is another disaster since the flooding mud is also blocking the river stream causing a barrier lake. However, this section will only explain the landslide animation. There are several approaches to do the animation, which are:

- Using particle to act as the mud
- Using the animated shader to imitate the muddy surface
- Using a simple plane movement

Experimenting on all of those techniques, the third is concluded as the most suitable techniques used for hololens. The first approach is too heavy for mobile computation. The detail on how to animate a particle could be found here: <https://docs.unity3d.com/ScriptReference/ParticleSystem.html> . By using the particle, the mud could easily be configured by setting up its physics parameter. The way to do it is by creating a transparent mesh that depicts an original hill before the landslide occurs. Then filling up the mesh with the mud particle. Once it finished, remove the mesh and the mud particle should fall individually from the hill flooding the village below it.

The second approach seems less heavy than the first one, but the hololens still could not render it well. The tutorial about using animated shader is all over the internet, including this official documentation: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/shader-StandardShader.html> . Actually the learning curve of playing with shader is high. So, it's better to skip this approach if the developer do not have a proper understanding. The point on this approach is to imitate mud movement only by changing the surface texture on a selected

plane without actually having the real mud particle. This sounds a really good idea that we do not exactly need to have any particle since the user only seeing the surface. That leads to the third idea.

Chosen as the best solution, the third animation approach is actually looking smooth and alive. The technique is as simple as moving the plane to the specific directions so it looks like a surface of the hill that moving down. However, there is a real challenge to design the plane so that it is similar to a real hill and has the right texture. The original plane is flat and the colour is white. By Using the terrain shaping tools, the simple plane is heightened and added some texture similar to its surrounding texture. The sense of art is needed on this part. The detail about shaping and colouring the plane will be covered on the next section.

c. Shaping and Contouring the Plane or Terrain

Working on the third technique, a new terrain or plane is needed to be created manually. In this report, the word terrain and plane are mentioned multiple times without any detail explanation. Basically, the terrain is a plane that has contour/height variation. So, the terms of “terrain” is similar to “plane” since all the plane used in this project are contoured and given any suitable texture. There are four additional planes/terrain in total called hill terrain, middle hill terrain, flooding mud terrain, and the barrier lake terrain. The detail on each role on those planes will be described in the next section. This explanation is only covering the technique to shape/contour the plane and give it some colour/texture. There is an official tutorial about this at: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/terrain-UsingTerrains.html> .

First of all, the empty flat terrain is need to be created by clicking 3D Object > Terrain. That original terrain is so big. It needs to be scaled down, look at the middle picture of the figure below for the detail parameter used in this project. After that, the plane should be shaped/contoured as needed using the tools available on the terrain inspector showed in the right picture below. The tutorial about contouring and colouring the terrain is also available on YouTube, entitled **Unity Tutorial 4 - How to apply materials, shaders and textures to objects in Unity** (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MGIBLPiz4oM>).

Figure 9 Creating a new terrain or plane, scaling down the plane, contouring, and then texturing the plane

The border is contoured manually from the flat plane so that it can match the height of Ab Barak terrain. It is like creating a cliff around the rectangular plane as shown in the figure below.

Figure 10 The border of Ab Barak terrain is made from a flat terrain using a shaping tools

d. Animating the Landslide

After finishing the contouring and colouring, the planes are ready to be animated. The explanation about terrain and plain is available at the previous section about contouring the plane or terrain. The figure below is showing the hill terrain. The animation is simply moving this object, hill terrain, mostly down towards the valley to simulate the landslide.

Figure 11 That additional piece of plane will simulate the landslide by moving it down slowly

The landslide animation actually is not well done without adding a flooding mud and a small piece of plane in the middle of the hill and the valley. The last piece is needed in order to have a smooth transition between the dropped hill and the mud that is coming up. The explanation in this report might not that clear. Therefore, you should watch the video first and then you will realize that the animation of the landslide is consists of 3 different plane animations.

Figure 12 The middle hill, the hill, and the flooding mud

The transition is not as simple as moving down or up, but it is a complex direction that is chosen after deciding the smoothest direction to perform the landslide animation. The moving animation is independent between those three object. The speed also configurable, but if the speed is changed, the frame count also need to be changed. Their animation are counted in a frame rate. For example, here is the code for animating the hill plane to go down:

```

1  using UnityEngine;
2  using System.Collections;
3
4  public class LandSlideGoesDown : MonoBehaviour
5  {
6      bool isPlaying;
7      Rigidbody playerRigidbody;
8      public float speed;
9      int frameCount;
10     Vector3 originalPosition;
11     float originalSpeed;
12
13
14     private void Start()
15     {
16         originalSpeed = speed;
17         isPlaying = true;
18         frameCount = 0;
19         originalPosition = this.transform.localPosition;
20         playerRigidbody = this.GetComponent<Rigidbody>();
21     }
22
23     void Update()
24     {
25         if (isPlaying)
26         {
27             // transform.Translate(Vector3.forward * speed);
28             if (frameCount < 840)
29             {
30                 speed = speed + speed / 500;
31
32                 transform.Translate(Vector3.back * speed * 1f);
33                 transform.Translate(Vector3.left * speed * 0.5f);
34                 transform.Translate(Vector3.down * speed * 0.4f);
35                 playerRigidbody.MovePosition(transform.position);
36                 frameCount++;
37             }
38         }
39         else
40         {
41             if (frameCount < 940)
42             {
43                 speed = speed + speed / 500;
44
45                 transform.Translate(Vector3.back * speed * 1.3f);
46                 transform.Translate(Vector3.left * speed * 0.6f);
47                 transform.Translate(Vector3.down * speed * 0.5f);
48                 playerRigidbody.MovePosition(transform.position);
49                 frameCount++;
50             }
51         }
52         else
53         {
54             if (frameCount < 1240)
55             {
56                 speed = speed + speed / 500;
57
58                 transform.Translate(Vector3.back * speed * 1.1f);
59                 transform.Translate(Vector3.left * speed * 0.8f);
60                 transform.Translate(Vector3.down * speed * 0.6f);
61                 playerRigidbody.MovePosition(transform.position);
62                 frameCount++;
63             }
64         }
65     }
66
67     // Called by SpeechManager when the user says the "Play" command
68     public void OnPlay()
69     {
70         isPlaying = true;
71     }
72
73     // Called by SpeechManager when the user says the "Pause" command
74     public void OnPause()
75     {
76         isPlaying = false;
77     }
78 }

```

Figure 13 Moving the hill down to the valley

Figure 14 The full terrain before and after the landslide happen

The scripts used in this entire project are stored at folder Scripts. For this plane animation, the object is moved based on quaternion vector position. The speed on each frame is vary. Those three objects (the middle hill, the hill, and the flooding mud) are attached to three different scripts. Each scripts define its behaviour towards the input from the user.

There are two additional method called onPlay and onPause if you look closely to the Figure 11. Those methods is corresponding to the broadcast message sent by the speech recognition manager. The detail on voice recognition implementation will be explained in the other section. In addition, the detail on object movement can be read at this following link, entitled “Transform.Translate”:

<https://docs.unity3d.com/ScriptReference/Transform.Translate.html>

Figure 15 Scripts folder

e. Adding the Barrier Lake

Barrier lake is the after effect of the landslide. The flooding mud is blocking the river stream and acting as an unwanted dam. The rain water is trapped and starting to flood the other side of the village creating another disaster on Ab Barak. Inferred from the previous section, this animation is done by using the third technique explained before. So, the first thing to do is shaping the flat plane to match the final looks of the flood. Then, starting the colouring process to imitate the colour of water mixed with the mud. Here are the comparison between each step until the final looks.

Figure 16 Contouring the plane/terrain with the shaping tools and applying some colour similar to water

Figure 17 Placing the "barrier lake" terrain to the desired place to show how the scene will look when the animation is finish

Inferred from the purpose of the barrier lake animation, the blue coloured terrain will be moved up towards its final position slowly. When the animation is started and the frame count is 1, the barrier lake haven't been showing up yet. It will start come up once the flooding mud “almost” finish. The animation order can

be seen easily by watching the demo video mentioned at the earlier section. The dominant colour of this barrier lake is blue, but it's actually not only blue. There are some other colour including brown to imitate the looks of the mud mixed with the rain water.

f. Displaying the Video, Image and Text

The other objects besides the terrain are a combination of video, image, and text. Those object are placed on canvas UI. The other UI component such as button, camera, and lighting, are not explained in this report since it is a fundamental knowledge on Unity. There are a lot of tutorial available on the internet about putting video, image, and text, such as:

- Movie Texture (<https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/class-MovieTexture.html>)
- Unity 5 UI Tutorial - How to Add Video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dWncJP6KMxc>)
- UI Image (<https://unity3d.com/learn/tutorials/topics/user-interface-ui/ui-image>)
- Unity 5 - From Beginner to Pro #44 - UI Image (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uew0zYUh3d0>)
- UI Text - Unity Official Tutorials (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wLY5sRewfVQ>)

Figure 18 Final layout that display the terrain as well as another information on the canvas

g. Applying Rain Animation

Rain animation is using particle system. There a lot of detail tutorial about using particle system, such as this one: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/PartSysUsage.html> . By changing its property and giving it a rain material, the particle will look like a pouring rain. We can specify the intensity, the number of particle, and even the size of each rain droplet. There are free raining prefabs in Unity Assets Store that can be downloaded. Beside configuring the raining animation, this project also plays a raining sound. The tutorial about putting the sound is available in these links:

- Sound Effects & Scripting (<https://unity3d.com/learn/tutorials/topics/audio/sound-effects-scripting>)
- Audio Source (<https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/class-AudioSource.html>)
- Programming / Adding sounds in Unity 5 (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iS0DTJfUuIA>)

Figure 19 Free rain assets

h. Applying Gesture Command

HoloLens has an accessory called clicker to interact with the user. However, it is only for clicking/selecting. It is recommended to use gesture. HoloLens can recognize the direction where the user is focusing, or gazing, and hand gestures. As an input, gazing at a specified area will highlight a button that the user focuses on. There are some possible hand gestures in HoloLens, for example clicking, dragging, and blooming but this project only implements one hand gesture to interact with, that is air tap gesture. Air tap gesture allows the user to click anywhere to take action. User is simply making a fist in front of him with the back of the hand facing him and then raising his index finger to the sky and tap, by flexing the index finger down and then back up.

Figure 20 Air tap gesture

HoloLens automatically translate a user air tap as mouse click, but the object that receive air tap should has a collider. Not every object has collider, checking and manually adding the collider are needed for some cases. For detail step by step explanation, there is a good tutorial in this following link: Holograms 211 (https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/holograms_211) .

i. Applying Voice Command

The other way to interact with HoloLens is by using voice commands. The command works by using command manager scripts that will receive all the command input and broadcast the message to the other object depends on the activated voice command. The detail tutorial about implementing the voice commands is presented on this link: Holograms 101 (https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/mixed-reality/holograms_101) .

us/windows/mixed-reality/holograms_101#chapter_4_-_voice). These are the voice commands that available in this project.

No.	Command	Description
a.	“Reset space”	To reset the whole scene in front of you
b.	“Pause animation”	To pause the landslide animation
c.	“Play animation”	To play or continue the landslide animation
d.	“Back”	To go back to the previous menu
e.	“Show help”	To show this information page
f.	“Close page”	To close this single page

Figure 21 Voice command

4. Evaluation

There is a bug in this project when it comes to spatial mapping feature. The HoloLens should be able to map the physical objects around the user, but this does not work. Thus, the HoloLens cannot put the simulation object on a physical object correctly. The virtual object can be put even intercepting with the physical object around it. Another evaluation for this project is to add another gesture or voice command so that the user can do more interaction such as rotating the 3D model and zooming in or out the 3D model.

5. Conclusion

This project about developing an animated 3D model of Ab-Barak landslide on HoloLens has been conducted well. The simulation shows the animated 3D model of landslide as well as the report and news about the disaster. The animation can be stopped, paused, or resumed using specified voice command that is informed in the help page. The development process of the simulation that has been well described in this report is useful for future works in order to develop a better simulation. In the future, this simulation can be widely used for educational purpose or even for training purpose.

6. Future Works

This project can be expanded into a greater simulation device by allowing more HoloLens to display the same view so that more people can see the same 3D model. Anyone using these connected HoloLens can see what the others doing with the 3D model. They can interaction to the model by adding texts or highlights or markers using a dedicated physical objects, such as pens or pencils. In conclusion, two features which are possible to be added are synchronizing more than one HoloLens and more interactive simulation.

7. Acknowledgement

First of all, I would like to express my deep gratitude for my supervisor, Bruno Silva de Sousa who had supervised me during the progression of my project as Openlab summer student. He had given me an opportunity to explore a new device which will be useful for future work at CERN and UNOSAT. Second, I would also like to thank Lars Bromley from UNOSAT who had entrusted this project to me and helped me during the time I was doing the project. I believe, the success of this project will be a great chance of further joint research between UNOSAT and CERN. The last but not least, it is my pleasure to work with Sebastian C. who gave me a lot of advices about the animation and the terrain.

8. Reference

- <https://unitar.org/the-institute>
- <https://unitar.org/unosat/>
- http://unosat-maps.web.cern.ch/unosat-maps/AF/FL20140430AFG/UNOSAT_Ab_Barak_landslide_report.pdf
- <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/hololens>

